

Can wind turbine blade waste be a feasible supplementary cementitious material from a chemical perspective?

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ABSTRACT

In order to solve the decommissioned wind turbine blades (WTBs) growing challenge, this study investigates the potential of using WTB waste (WTBW) materials as supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) in concrete. Three different WTBW were characterized using X-ray fluorescence (XRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), thermogravimetric analysis-derivative thermogravimetry (TGA-DTG), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), R³ calorimetry, and leaching tests. Results show WTBW exhibiting pozzolanic activity with limited release of potentially harmful elements (Cr, Cu, Mo, Pb, and V) under EU standard limits, suggesting their suitability as SCMs. This study establishes the technical feasibility of repurposing diverse WTBW sources as SCMs, identifying that while all sources possess pozzolanic potential, WTBW1 and WTBW2 offer superior reactivity due to better glass exposure. These findings provide a critical framework for source-specific characterizing strategies to predict the integration of WTBW into sustainable concrete production.

1. Introduction

The use of WTBW as a construction material is gaining attention worldwide, with many researchers exploring its potential applications [1,2]. This approach offers a promising solution to the growing environmental concern of landfilling decommissioned blades [3]. Currently, WTBW recycling is categorized into three major techniques: mechanical, chemical, and thermal recycling [2,4]. Mechanical recycling is more energy-efficient than pyrolysis or solvolysis, making the use of ground WTBW a low-carbon alternative for supplementary cementitious material (SCM) production [5]. Previous studies have summarized the potential benefits of using WTBW as SCMs, highlighting their potential to reduce reliance on traditional cement production and decrease the environmental impact of concrete construction [1,2]. However, the composition of WTBW can vary significantly depending on the manufacturer and blade type, making it crucial to assess the properties of each material through experimental investigation [6]. Furthermore, it is essential to evaluate the safety and suitability of using WTBW as SCMs to ensure long-term durability and minimize any potential environmental risks [6,7]. Despite the recognized potential of WTBW as a sustainable

construction material, significant uncertainty remains regarding how its highly variable composition affects the long-term structural integrity and environmental safety of cementitious composites as SCMs.

While the composition of WTBs varies, they generally consist of glass fibers embedded in a resin matrix [8,9]. Glass (the fundamental chemistry of glass fiber) is already widely used as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM), suggesting that WTBW has the potential to serve a similar purpose [10]. Glass fibers are primarily amorphous silica (SiO₂) and alumina (Al₂O₃). In the high pH environment of cement (pH > 12.5), these amorphous phases dissolve and react with calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) to form calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gels within the cementitious matrix [11,12]. Fine WTBW may contribute to both nucleation sites for cement hydration as a filler material and react chemically over time [9]. However, the specific composition of WTBs can differ significantly due to variations in manufacturing processes and blade design [13]. Previous studies have reported different contents of glass in WTBW [14,15], and the type of resin used can also vary, with both epoxy [16,17] and polyester resins [18] being common. These variations in composition can lead to differences in the properties of WTBW when incorporated into construction materials. Moreover, Liu

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et al. [2] reported that WTBW exhibits pozzolanic activity through a systematic review, summarizing the reaction mechanisms of WTBW in cementitious materials, including the role of glass fiber and resin content in the high pH environment of the cementitious matrix. While the pozzolanic potential of pure glass fibers is well-documented, the presence of cross-linked polymer resins in WTBW creates a complex multi-component system whose hydration kinetics and interfacial bonding remain poorly understood [9]. However, there is limited literature on directly testing the reactivity of WTBW. The Rapid, Relevant, and Reliable (R^3) test is a valuable tool for evaluating the reactivity of powdered materials intended for use as SCMs, providing insights into their potential contribution to strength development and overall performance in concrete [19]. To summarize, it is essential to characterize the chemical composition of WTBW from different sources to understand its potential as an SCM. Furthermore, the activity of these WTBWs needs to be assessed to confirm their suitability for use in cementitious applications. Besides the technical assessment of the raw materials, construction materials must also fulfill environmental requirements [20]. Revilla-Cuesta et al. [21] investigated the use of raw-crushed wind turbine blades in concrete production and found that while strength decreased with increasing WTBW content, potentially leaching harmful elements (e.g., Cu and Pb) remained an important issue requiring further evaluation. Zhang et al. [22] also reported that, to date, this aspect has received limited attention. Therefore, a leaching analysis of different raw WTBW powders is crucial to understanding whether they are safe for use as SCMs in cement or concrete matrices.

This study aims to understand the feasibility of using WTBW as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM) in cement or concrete. To achieve this, we conducted a comprehensive characterization of three WTBWs obtained from different sources, focusing on their chemical composition (XRF), mineralogy (XRD and FTIR), microstructure (SEM), thermal properties (TGA and DSC), reactivity (R^3 Calorimetry), and leaching behavior. Our results demonstrate the suitability of WTBW as an SCM and highlight the potential contributions of this approach to sustainable construction practices.

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials

Table 1 presents the chemical compositions of the WTBW materials, analyzed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF). The table shows the weight percentages of various oxides present in three different groups, labeled WTBW1, WTBW2, and WTBW3. The WTBWs were sourced from Spain and Denmark. To ensure feedstock homogeneity and high mineral purity, the raw WTBW used in this study was pre-processed by the industrial supplier to remove lightweight “core” materials, such as balsa wood and structural foams. This was achieved via an industrial-scale water separation process designed to isolate the glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP).

Significant differences in composition were observed among the groups. For instance, CaO content differed notably, with WTBW1 and WTBW3 having higher percentages (26.77% and 27.86%, respectively) than WTBW2 (18.94%). Similarly, the MgO content varied considerably, with WTBW2 showing a much higher percentage (6.94%) compared to WTBW1 (2.09%) and WTBW3 (1.71%).

The SiO_2 content was relatively consistent across all groups, ranging from 56.10% to 58.24%. The loss on ignition (LOI) values, indicating the

amount of volatile substances of organic resins, were also high across all samples, particularly in WTBW3 (56.00%). These variations in chemical composition are important to consider when evaluating the potential of these materials for use in cementitious applications.

The particle size distribution (PSD) of different WTBW is shown in Fig. 1. The received shredded wind turbine blade waste that was ground in a Planetary Ball Mill PM 400 for 5 min at 200 rpm exhibited different size distributions. PSD analysis was used with the Mastersizer 3000 + in dry powder mode. Specifically, WTBW1 (solid black line) is a unimodal distribution with a D_{50} of 25.4 μm . WTBW2 (solid red line) is a shifted bimodal distribution with a D_{50} of 15.2 μm , indicating a finer product. Finally, WTBW3 (solid blue line) is a wider bimodal distribution with a higher concentration of larger particles and a D_{50} of 23.6 μm . The corresponding cumulative distributions for each sample are also shown.

2.2. Test methods

The raw material processing, test protocols, and evaluation methods are shown in Fig. 2. Detailed testing methods are as follows.

2.2.1. X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis

Three different WTBW materials were finely ground to ensure homogeneity before analysis. Detailed information is in the Section 2.1 in terms of PSD description. For XRF, 1 g of WTBW was mixed with 10 g of flux (99.5% lithium tetraborate and 0.5% lithium iodide). The mixture was fused in a platinum or platinum–gold crucible at 950–1100 $^{\circ}C$ for 25 min to obtain a molten solution. The molten mixture was then poured into a preheated mold and cooled to form a fused glass bead. The prepared bead was analyzed using a LeNeo Fluxer XRF spectrometer to determine the oxide composition.

2.2.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis

The phase composition of the three WTBW powders was analyzed using an X'Pert PRO diffractometer (Co– $K\alpha$ radiation, 40 kV, 30 mA). The scanning range was set from 5 $^{\circ}$ to 70 $^{\circ}$ (2 θ). The obtained diffraction patterns were used to identify the crystalline phases using Highscore software present in the WTBW samples. The ground powder was

Fig. 1. PSD of wind turbine blade waste from different sources.

Table 1
Material compositions.

Group	Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	Cr ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	Others	LOI*
WTBW1	0.46	2.09	10.92	56.20	0.09	0.75	0.27	26.77	0.73	0.06	0.63	1.01	36.50
WTBW2	0.53	6.94	13.40	58.24	0.08	0.67	-	18.94	0.42	0.02	0.54	0.23	33.50
WTBW3	0.70	1.71	10.90	56.10	0.06	0.87	0.07	27.86	0.68	-	0.21	0.85	56.00

Fig. 2. Experimental workflow and visual evidence of the mechanical processing of WTBW sources.

processed by the same procedure as PSD.

2.2.3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The morphology and microstructure of the three WTBW powders were examined using a Quanta FEI FEG-250 scanning electron microscope operated at 15 kV with a backscatter detector. Before observation, the powdered samples were coated with a 20 nm layer of palladium to enhance conductivity and image quality.

2.2.4. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis was performed using a NicoletTM iS50 spectrometer with a wavenumber range of 500–4000 cm^{-1} with 32 scans with a resolution of 8 cm^{-1} . The powdered raw material samples were prepared following the same procedure as PSD. The fine powder was directly placed onto the diamond crystal of the Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) accessory.

2.2.5. Thermal analysis

Thermogravimetric (TGA) and derivative (DTG) analysis was performed on a Discovery TGA from TA Instruments in a nitrogen atmosphere with a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ from 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 900 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The weight of the powdered specimen was 10–20 mg. The powdered raw material samples were prepared following the same procedure as mentioned in XRF.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed on a Discovery DSC from TA Instruments in a nitrogen atmosphere with a heating and cooling rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ from -90°C to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to determine the glass transition (T_g) and decomposition temperatures. T_g was calculated by means of a heating scan as the temperature of the halfway point of the jump in heat capacity. The weight of the specimen was 2–5 mg.

2.2.6. Rapid, relevant, and reliable (R^3) test

The hydration behavior of WTBW was evaluated using the Rapid, Relevant, and Reliable (R^3) test, which is a rapid method for measuring the chemical reactivity of SCMs [23]. The test was performed at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ instead of the standard 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [24] to simulate the ambient temperature of using SCM with an isothermal calorimeter (I-Cal Flex), and the heat release was monitored continuously from the beginning of the mixing to

168 h to assess hydration kinetics. The mix design of R^3 test and the compositions of the potassium solution are listed in Table 2.

2.2.7. Leaching test

Leaching behavior was tested using a solid-to-liquid ratio of 1:10 (g/mL) in deionized water according to EN 12457 [25]. The mixture was shaken at 200 rpm for 24 h. After shaking, the leachate was filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane filter and acidified with a few drops of 1 M HNO_3 to acidify the solution. The concentrations of selected metal ions (Cu, Cr, Mo, Pb, and V) were determined using an Agilent 5800 ICP-OES instrument.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Fig. 3 presents the X-ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns used to identify the mineral phases within the raw waste turbine blade (WTB) materials.

Sample WTBW3 showed the most complex crystalline composition. The main phase identified was calcite (CaCO_3), which corresponds to the highest peaks and matches the reference pattern (01-072-4582). This is due to the filler materials from the blade manufacturing [26,27]. Additionally, WTBW3 contained rutile (TiO_2), which is used as a coating on the surface of the blade [28], indicated by peaks aligning with the reference pattern (01-079-5860). The text notes that both calcite and rutile likely come from the filler materials used in the WTB. Notably, WTBW3 also exhibited distinct peaks corresponding to s-triazine ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{N}_3$) matching the reference pattern (00-031-1954). Sample

Table 2
Mix design of R^3 test (unit:g).

Component	Material	Mass ratio (per unit WTBW)
Solid precursors	WTBW	1.00
	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$	3.00
	CaCO_3	0.50
Alkaline solution	Total solution	5.40
	KOH	0.02
	K_2SO_4	0.11
	Distilled water	5.27

Fig. 3. XRD of wind turbine blade waste from different sources.

WTBW2 showed a simpler crystalline profile. The primary crystalline phase identified was rutile (TiO_2), similar to its presence in WTBW3. Unlike WTBW3, WTBW2 showed no significant peaks for calcite or s-triazine. In sample WTBW1, the dominant crystalline phase identified was quartz (SiO_2), with prominent peaks aligning with the reference pattern (03-065-0466). This quartz is suggested to originate from the crystalline phases within the glass fiber content of the blade. These filaments are typically produced with diameters ranging from 0.5 to 30 μm , originating from molten silica, which contains approximately 50–60% SiO_2 . Consequently, the high silica content and the manufacturing process of these glass fibers result in the presence of quartz as a residual crystalline phase within WTBW [29]. WTBW1 did not show significant peaks for calcite, rutile, or s-triazine. A common and important feature across all three samples (WTBW1, WTBW2, and WTBW3) is the presence of a broad, diffused hump centered roughly between 15° and $30^\circ 2\theta$. This broad peak indicates the presence of a substantial amount of amorphous Si content from the glass fiber used in the blade material. The results confirm that while the crystalline phases differ (WTBW3 is dominated by calcite, WTBW1 by quartz, and WTBW2

by rutile/amorphous content), all materials contain varying amounts of this key amorphous silicate component. These distinct crystalline and amorphous compositions are expected to significantly influence how each material reacts when mixed into cementitious systems.

3.2. Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

Fig. 4 presents SEM images of WTBW obtained from three sources, including WTBW1, WTBW2, and WTBW3, using a backscatter detector at magnifications of $500\times$ and $1000\times$. The micrographs show clear differences in the distribution and morphology of the glass fibers and resin components among the samples.

At $500\times$ magnification (Fig. 4a–c), WTBW1 sample displays relatively long and well-defined glass fibers embedded in a resin matrix. The fibers appear smooth and continuous, with some resin fragments adhering to their surfaces. In contrast, WTBW2 sample shows shorter and more irregularly distributed fibers surrounded by fragmented resin particles, suggesting partial grinding separation of components during processing. WTBW3 sample exhibits a more compact and heterogeneous morphology, where the resin phase dominates and the glass fibers are less visible, indicating a higher degree of fragmentation or resin coverage. At $1000\times$ magnification (Fig. 4d–f), the microstructure becomes clearer. WTBW1 sample retains distinct fiber-resin interfaces with some residual resin coating on the fibers. The red arrow in Fig. 4(a) shows the glass fiber completely covered with resin, indicating poor fiber exposure. WTBW2 sample shows rough fiber surfaces with resin residues attached, suggesting surface damage or incomplete cleaning. The red arrow in Fig. 4(b) shows the separate glass fiber and resin. WTBW3 sample reveals a dense resin matrix with embedded fine glass fragments (red arrow in Fig. 4(c)), showing poor fiber exposure compared to WTBW1 and WTBW2. WTBW1 presents the most distinguishable glass fiber structure, while WTBW3 demonstrates the most compact resin-rich morphology.

3.3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR results of three different WTBW sources are presented in Fig. 5, with spectrum information in Table 3 and Table 4. All three

Fig. 4. SEM of wind turbine blade waste by backscatter detector (a) WTBW1 $500\times$; (b) WTBW2 $500\times$; (c) WTBW3 $500\times$; (d) WTBW1 $1000\times$; (e) WTBW2 $1000\times$; (f) WTBW3 $1000\times$.

Fig. 5. FTIR of wind turbine blade waste from different sources.

Table 3
Bands from the FTIR spectrum from different WTBW sources.

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Band	Material type
700	Aromatic CHS rings	Polyester resin
744	-O-O- peroxide group	Polyester resin
828	C-H p-benzene	Epoxy resin
876	C-H Aromatic	Epoxy resin
1014	Si-O-Si	Glass fiber
1269	C-O-C Asymmetric	Polyester resin
1725	C=O ester	Polyester resin

Table 4
Relative content of different compositions from different WTBW sources (↑represents relative content).

Waste source	Epoxy resin	Polyester resin	Glass fibers
WTBW1	↑↑↑	↑	↑↑
WTBW2	-	↑↑↑	↑↑↑
WTBW3	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑

WTBW show the strong Si-O-Si vibrations at 1014 cm⁻¹, demonstrating the glass fiber silicate framework for the raw composites [30]. WTBW2 and WTBW3 spectra display strong aromatic CHS rings vibrations at ~700 and -O-O- peroxide group vibrations at ~744 cm⁻¹, confirming the existence of polyester [31]. Polymer bands differentiate the sources: epoxy-related peaks at ~828 cm⁻¹ (p-substituted benzene C-H) [32,33] and ~876 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C-H) [34] are pronounced in WTBW1 and WTBW3, but weak/absent in WTBW2; polyester-related bands at ~1269 cm⁻¹ (asymmetric C-O-C) [35] and ~1725 cm⁻¹ (ester C=O) [36] are strongest in WTBW2 and weaker in WTBW1 and WTBW3. The relative intensities in Table 4 indicate higher epoxy content in WTBW1 and WTBW3, whereas WTBW2 is polyester-rich and shows the clearest glass signatures. The qualitative comparison presented in Table 3 is derived from the relative intensities of characteristic FTIR absorption bands, where peak magnitudes serve as a proxy for the concentration of specific organic and mineral functional groups across the samples.

These assignments are consistent with broader characterization. The stronger polymer signals in WTBW1 and 3 align with their higher organic burden from thermal analysis and with resin-coated textures in SEM, while the clearer glass exposure in WTBW2 matches its finer morphology and better dispersion. Together with the XRD evidence of an amorphous glass phase, the FTIR results confirm that all wastes share a silicate framework but differ in resin type and amount, helping to explain the source-dependent trends in early reactivity and

processability observed elsewhere in this study.

3.4. Thermal analysis

Fig. 6 shows the thermal behavior of wind turbine blade waste (WTBW) from three sources (WTBW1, WTBW2, and WTBW3) analyzed using thermogravimetric analysis-derivative thermogravimetry (TGA-DTG) from 40°C to 900°C, and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) from -90°C to 250°C.

In the TGA-DTG curves (Fig. 6a), all samples exhibit two main stages of weight loss. The first stage occurs between 200°C and 400°C, corresponding to the decomposition of organic resin components [37]. The second stage, appearing between 400°C and 650°C, is mainly associated with the breakdown of residual carbonaceous matter and calcite decomposition [38,39]. Among the samples, WTBW3 shows the highest overall mass loss, indicating a higher organic content, while WTBW1 retains the most stable residue, suggesting a higher glass fiber or inorganic fraction. The derivative weight (DTG) peaks further confirm that the main degradation takes place in these two stages.

The DSC curves (Fig. 6b) further support the thermal transitions observed in TGA. Each sample shows a glass transition (T_g) followed by a major exothermic decomposition peak. The T_g values are around 52.7°C (WTBW1), 63.3°C (WTBW2), and 58.6°C (WTBW3), indicating variations in resin composition and curing degree. The decomposition temperatures appear at approximately 134.6°C (WTBW1), 165.8°C (WTBW2), and 197.8°C (WTBW3), with corresponding enthalpy changes of 13.804 J/g, 9.476 J/g, and 10.882 J/g, respectively. These differences reflect the diverse polymer matrices and filler contents in the blade wastes from different sources.

WTBW1 shows the lowest T_g and decomposition temperature, suggesting a less cross-linked or partially cured resin, while WTBW3 demonstrates the highest thermal stability, which may result from a higher degree of curing or different resin/hardener formulation.

3.5. Rapid, relevant, and reliable (R^3) test

These are the results of the Rapid, Relevant, and Reliable (R^3) test conducted at 20°C. The heat release over time (Fig. 7) showed distinct hydration patterns for the three WTBW materials analyzed under potassium solution. Initial wetting of WTBW was observed after mixing with the potassium solution.

In Fig. 7(a), WTBW1 showed the strongest early heat response, with a rapid increase in heat release within the first few hours. However, this early heat evolution should not be interpreted solely as true pozzolanic reactivity. At the initial stage of the R^3 test, the heat signal may also include contributions from wetting, particle packing, surface dissolution, and nucleation/filler effects [40,41], especially when more glass surfaces are exposed. Therefore, the early heat response mainly reflects the accessibility and surface activity of the WTBW particles rather than only the extent of chemical reaction. In contrast, the later cumulative heat release provides a more reliable indication of chemical reactivity. The continued increase in heat release at later ages suggests the progressive dissolution of silicate and aluminate species from the glass phase and the subsequent formation of secondary reaction products. Compared to the other WTBW materials, WTBW1 exhibited the strongest initial heat response, indicating higher surface accessibility and early physical/nucleation contribution. WTBW3 also reacted quickly, following a similar initial curve to WTBW1 but reaching a lower peak heat release of about 80 J/g. Its overall activity was clearly less intense than WTBW1. The WTBW2 material was unique because its reaction was heavily delayed. For the first few hours, its heat release remained almost negligible, staying near zero. It only began a sharp, rapid increase after approximately 10 h. This late start suggests a very slow initiation or a different, delayed reaction mechanism. Looking closely at the later stages (100–170 h) in the inset, we see continued activity. The initially slow-releasing WTBW2 material continued its steep climb, eventually

Fig. 6. Wind turbine blade waste from different sources (a) TGA-DTG from 40°C to 900°C; (b) DSC from -90 °C to 250°C.

Fig. 7. Reactivity of wind turbine blade waste from different sources (a) total heat release; (b) heat flow.

approaching the final total heat release of the WTBW1 material, ending up near 100 J/g by the 168-hour mark. In contrast, WTBW3 heat release leveled off significantly earlier, hovering around 80 J/g.

The isothermal calorimetry results for the normalized heat flow are presented in Fig. 7(b), illustrating the early-age heat release kinetics of different WTBW samples. Both WTBW1 and WTBW3 show a typical heat release profile with a significant main peak occurring within the first hour. In contrast, WTBW2 exhibits a severe retardation effect, where the initial hydration peak is almost entirely suppressed, only showing a minor heat flow signal after approximately 0.5 h. This delayed reaction in WTBW2 correlates with its specific polyester resin properties, which likely inhibit the early-stage dissolution of the glass content. However, despite this initial slowness, the samples eventually achieve competitive total heat release as shown in Fig. 7(a).

These noticeable differences in the speed, intensity, and final heat totals clearly demonstrate that WTBW1, WTBW2, and WTBW3 have varying reactivity levels, and their contributions to the final cement system will differ greatly based on when they begin to hydrate in this R^3 test setup. Most importantly, all three WTBW sources show apparent reactivity in the R^3 system, with later cumulative heat release suggesting a certain degree of chemical reactivity associated with glass dissolution.

3.6. Leaching

The leaching characteristics of wind turbine blade waste from three sources, WTBW1, WTBW2, and WTBW3, were analyzed at a liquid-to-solid ratio of 10:1 (Table 5) according to EN 12457 [25]. The results showed that aluminum concentrations ranged from 0.49 mg/L (WTBW2) to 0.90 mg/L (WTBW3), while calcium exhibited substantial variation, with WTBW2 recording the highest value (176.74 mg/L). Chromium (Cr) and copper (Cu) concentrations remained below the EU leaching limits (0.63 mg/L and 0.9 mg/L, respectively), with Cr between 0.003–0.006 mg/L and Cu between 0.088–0.164 mg/L. Lead (Pb) was most pronounced in WTBW2 (0.15 mg/L) and vanadium (V) was most pronounced in WTBW1 (0.005 mg/L), which were far lower than the limits of 1.2 mg/L and 1.8 mg/L. Molybdenum (Mo) was only detected in WTBW2 (0.006 mg/L), below the 1 mg/L limit. Phosphorus concentrations were generally low (<0.1 mg/L). The results indicate limited leaching potential for all elements, suggesting low environmental impact under the test conditions.

While the elemental analysis in Table 5 confirms that selected heavy metals (Cr, Cu, Mo, Pb, V) remain well below regulatory limits, it is important to note that this environmental assessment is not yet exhaustive. Wind turbine blades consist of complex polymer matrices and chemical additives that may pose risks beyond inorganic leaching. Due to current laboratory equipment constraints, specific organic

Table 5
Leaching of wind turbine blade waste from different sources(mg/L).

Groups	WTBW1		WTBW2		WTBW3		Limits [25]
	Ave*	STD*	Ave	STD	Ave	STD	
Al	0.700	0.036	0.490	0.019	0.896	0.017	-
Ca	14.400	0.198	176.740	2.962	12.536	0.213	-
Cr	0.003	0.001	0.006	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.63
Cu	0.164	0.002	0.127	0.003	0.088	0.002	0.9
K	22.426	1.578	12.218	0.409	20.553	0.644	-
Mg	0.414	0.046	0.171	0.005	1.834	0.019	-
Mo	UDL*	UDL	0.006	0.000	0.002	0.000	1
Na	26.390	0.493	2.801	0.024	20.663	0.064	-
P	0.097	0.005	0.037	UDL	0.014	0.000	-
Pb	0.046	0.012	0.150	0.075	0.029	0.026	1.2
Si	17.920	0.249	13.695	0.299	2.790	0.052	-
Sr	0.028	0.003	1.270	0.018	0.020	0.002	-
Ti	0.026	0.015	UDL	UDL	0.006	0.003	-
V	0.005	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.001	0.000	1.8

Ave* = Average results

STD* = Standard deviation

UDL* = Under detection limit

leachables were not quantified in this study, such as Total Organic Carbon (TOC), phenolics, or epoxy-related species. We acknowledge this as a limitation in the current characterization of WTBW. The future research plan includes performing comprehensive organic leaching tests. This can involve using GC-MS or specialized TOC analyzers to monitor the long-term stability of the polymer-degradation products under various environmental conditions (different pH), ensuring the holistic safety of these materials when reused as SCMs.

3.7. Comprehensive evaluation of each material

The SCM potential of the three WTBW sources was assessed using five simple indices that capture chemistry, organic burden, apparent cumulative reactivity, processability, and environmental compliance. The detailed index information and the evaluation of SCM potential are as follows:

3.7.1. Chemical pozzolanicity index (CPI)

As described in ref [42], the major reactive oxides are Na₂O, MgO, Al₂O₃, SiO₂, SO₃, K₂O, CaO, and Fe₂O₃. The degree of reaction of the ashes was calculated by the reactive glassy content determined by XRF and quantitative XRD. In our case, the glassy content of glass fiber is almost all amorphous, therefore we roughly used the SiO₂-Al₂O₃-Fe₂O₃ (SAF) fraction as pozzolanic phases, as shown in Eq. (1). Here, CPI is a simple chemistry-based indicator of pozzolanic potential for our case. It compares the amount of acidic, glass-forming oxides as shown in Eq. (1). A higher CPI indicates a composition richer in reactive siliceous/aluminous phases and, therefore, better chemical suitability as an SCM.

$$CPI = \frac{SiO_2 + Al_2O_3 + Fe_2O_3}{CaO + MgO + Na_2O + K_2O + SO_3} \quad (1)$$

Table 6 lists the oxide group sums and the resulting CPI for the three WTBW samples. WTBW2 shows the highest CPI (2.67) due to a larger SiO₂-Al₂O₃-Fe₂O₃ fraction and lower basic oxides, indicating the strongest chemical potential for pozzolanic behavior. WTBW1 has a CPI of 2.23, suggesting moderate potential, while WTBW3 has the lowest

Table 6

CPI of wind turbine blade waste from different sources.

	SiO ₂ + Al ₂ O ₃ + Fe ₂ O ₃ (wt%)	CaO + MgO + Na ₂ O + K ₂ O + SO ₃ (wt %)	CPI
WTBW1	67.75	30.34	2.23
WTBW2	72.18	27.08	2.67
WTBW3	67.21	31.21	2.15

CPI (2.15) among the three but still indicates usable pozzolanic chemistry.

3.7.2. Resin burden index (RBI)

RBI quantifies how much organic resin remains in the waste and how strongly it may interfere with cement hydration [43]. It uses loss on organic content (LOO) between 200 and 650°C from TGA (shown in Eq. 2). For comparison across samples, RBI is normalized to a 0–1 score (higher is better) by inverting and min–max scaling:

$$RBI_i = \frac{\text{Max}(LOO) - LOO_i}{\text{Max}(LOO) - \text{Min}(LOO)} \quad (2)$$

Table 7 lists LOO and normalized RBI. WTBW2 has the highest RBI (1) indicating the smallest resin burden. WTBW1 is intermediate RBI (0.615). WTBW3 shows the lowest RBI (0), reflecting substantial organics and the greatest likelihood of hydration interference. Practically, WTBW2 is ready for SCM use, WTBW1 may need moderate grinding or mild heat treatment, and WTBW3 would benefit most from pretreatment to reduce LOO before use as a reactive SCM. Table 7 also shows the RBIs calculated from the literature. It means the burden from organic matters in WTBW varies.

3.7.3. R³ reactivity index (RRI)

RRI measures the early pozzolanic activity of WTBW relative to a reference calcined clay in the R³ test. It is defined at a fixed age as the ratio of cumulative heat release of the sample to that of the reference (Eq. 4). Here, Q_{ref} CC(160 h) is the cumulative heat at 160 h for a benchmark calcined clay (95% of calcined kaolinite content) at 20 °C, taken from the literature source [47]. A higher RRI indicates stronger apparent cumulative reactivity under the selected R³ conditions, while

Table 7

RBI of wind turbine blade waste from different sources and comparing with literature.

	LOO (%)	RBI	Note	Ref
WTBW1	35.7	0.615	-	-
WTBW2	29.2	1	-	-
WTBW3	46.1	0	-	-
Glass fiber reinforced plastic	44.9	0.07	From rooflights and cladding	[44]
Fiber reinforced polymer	42.96	0.19	Not mentioned the origin of this waste	[45]
Glass fiber-reinforced thermoset	24.7	1.27	retired wind turbine blades	[46]

the distinction between early physical effects and later chemical reaction should be considered when interpreting the results.

$$RRI_{160} = \frac{Q_{WTBW}(160h)}{Q_{ref\ CC}(160h)} \quad (4)$$

Table 8 reports the cumulative heats at 160 h and the resulting RRI using $Q_{ref\ CC}(160\ h) = 225\ J$. WTBW1, WTBW2, and WTBW3 reach 44.95%, 43.07%, and 35.05% of the cumulative heat release of the reference calcined clay, respectively. [47]. Thus, WTBW1 and WTBW2 show comparable moderate early activity, while WTBW3 is clearly less reactive in the R^3 system.

3.7.4. SEM processability index (SPI) – quick image-based score

The SEM Processability Index (SPI) is a quick image-based score used to judge how readily a WTBW powder will disperse and act as a nucleation/filler aid in cement. It combines two visual cues from SEM: the apparent particle size, classified as coarse, medium, or fine, and the degree of glass exposure relative to resin coating on particle surfaces. These observations are converted to a simple 0–1 scale, where 1 reflects fine particles with high glass exposure (best processability), 0.5 indicates mixed features such as medium fineness or partial resin films, and 0 marks coarse, resin-rich particles with low glass exposure. Applying this scheme (shown in Table 9), WTBW2 scores 1.0, showing fine, well-exposed glass fragments and the most favorable processability; WTBW1 scores 0.5, consistent with a mixed morphology where some fine fragments are present but resin films and fiber pieces remain; and WTBW3 scores 0.0, reflecting coarser, resin-covered particles that would likely require additional grinding or pretreatment.

3.7.5. Leaching compliance score (LCS)

The Leaching Compliance Score (LCS) summarizes environmental suitability based on metal release in the leaching test. It converts the measured concentrations of key elements such as Cu, Cr, and Pb into a simple 0–1 scale: a value of 1 indicates the sample meets the regulatory limits, 0.5 signals values close to the limits, and 0 means the limits are exceeded and pretreatment or encapsulation is needed before use. Under this criterion, WTBW1, WTBW2, and WTBW3 each score 1, showing compliant leachate levels at the test conditions (as shown in Table 10).

3.7.6. Final comparison

Fig. 8 compares the three WTBW sources using normalized indices for chemistry (CPI), reactivity (RRI), resin burden (RBI), processability (SPI), and environmental compliance (LCS). All the normalized scores can be found in Table A1. The WTBW2 plot is close to a full pentagon: chemistry reaches the maximum, reactivity is high, the resin-burden score is at the top, processability is also at the top, and the environmental score is 1. The WTBW1 plot is slightly contracted: chemistry and reactivity remain high and the environmental score is 1, while the resin-burden score and processability are moderate, giving a narrower face on those axes. The WTBW3 plot is the most compact: chemistry is moderate, reactivity is lower, the resin-burden score is near zero, processability is low, and the environmental score is 1. The integrated scores rank the SCM potential as $WTBW2 > WTBW1 > WTBW3$, consistent with the individual test outcomes.

Table 11 lists the basic characteristics of different WTBW sources and their perspective on potential applications. Drawing on the physical, chemical, mineral, and morphological traits reported in [48], WTBW1 shows particles of similar size and low specific gravity with a fiber-like

Table 8
RRI of wind turbine blade waste from different sources.

	$Q_{WTBW}(160\ h)$ (J)	$Q_{ref\ CC}(160\ h)$ (J)	RRI (%)
WTBW1	101.13	225	44.95
WTBW2	96.916		43.07
WTBW3	78.871		35.05

Table 9
SPI of wind turbine blade waste from different sources.

Source	Particle Size (Visual)	Glass Exposure vs. Resin Coating	SPI Score	Processing Implications
WTBW2	Fine	High glass exposure; minimal resin interference.	1.0	Best processability; optimal for nucleation/filler aid.
WTBW1	Medium	Mixed morphology; partial resin films and fiber pieces.	0.5	Moderate processability; acceptable for general use.
WTBW3	Coarse	High resin coverage; low glass surface availability.	0.0	Poor processability; requires additional grinding/pretreatment.

morphology and a medium amorphous fraction. In Fig. 8, the chemistry and reactivity scores are high and leaching is compliant, while the resin-related and processability scores are mid-range. The combination suggests that WTBW1 can function as a workability-modifying addition, where the relatively larger, regular particles assist flow [49,50], and as a moderate pozzolanic replacement when dosage is controlled to mitigate residual resin and fiber pieces due to silicate and aluminate content in the glass fiber [51–53]. Quartz from the glass fibers is the dominant crystalline phase, with a broad amorphous hump indicating glassy silica. Strong Si–O–Si bands ($\sim 700, 744\ cm^{-1}$) confirm the glass phase; epoxy markers ($\sim 828, 876\ cm^{-1}$) are evident, while polyester bands ($\sim 1269, 1725\ cm^{-1}$) are weaker, which is consistent with a moderate organic burden.

WTBW2 consists of fine, irregular particles with a relatively high amorphous content. Its evaluation polygon in Fig. 8 is broad on all axes: chemistry and reactivity are high, the resin burden is low, processability is maximal, and leaching is compliant. These features indicate strength-modifying use through enhanced nucleation and early hydration, and support reactive SCM replacement at higher levels due to accessible glassy phases and easy dispersion [54–56]. The amorphous hump from XRD is pronounced, pointing to abundant reactive glass. Simultaneously, Si–O–Si bands are clear, while polyester signatures ($\sim 1269, 1725\ cm^{-1}$) are strong and epoxy signals are weak/absent, matching the low resin burden seen thermally and the good glass exposure seen in SEM.

WTBW3 presents fine but irregular particles with a lower amorphous fraction caused by higher resin content. Also shown in Fig. 8, the chemistry of WTBW3 is acceptable and leaching passes, whereas reactivity and processability are low and the resin score is near zero. The high resin content hinders the cement hydration if use it as SCM in the matrix [57,58]. The profile fits set-retarding or filler-type applications, with pozzolanic use only after pretreatment (e.g., thermal cleaning and/or additional grinding) to reduce resin films and expose glass surfaces for reaction. The amorphous hump from XRD is less pronounced than in WTBW2. And along with Si–O–Si bands, both epoxy ($\sim 828, 876\ cm^{-1}$) and polyester ($\sim 1269, 1725\ cm^{-1}$) features are visible, aligning with the higher organic content and the resin-rich textures observed by SEM.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

This paper assessed whether WTBW from different sources (WTBW1, WTBW2, WTBW3) can serve as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM) by analyzing phase assemblage (XRD), microstructure (SEM), fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), thermal behavior (TGA–DTG/DSC), early-age reactivity (R^3), and leaching. The results indicate technical feasibility for SCM use, with source-specific processing or dosage control to manage organics and maximize accessible glass. The following detailed conclusions can be drawn:

Table 10
LCS of wind turbine blade waste from different sources.

Elements	WTBW1	Note	LCS	WTBW2	Note	LCS	WTBW3	Note	LCS	Limits from standard [25]
Cr	0.003	L*	1	0.006	L	1	0.005	L	1	0.63
Cu	0.164	L	1	0.127	L	1	0.088	L	1	0.9
Mo	UDL*	L	1	0.006	L	1	0.002	L	1	1
Pb	0.046	L	1	0.150	L	1	0.029	L	1	1.2
V	0.005	L	1	0.004	L	1	0.001	L	1	1.8

*L = Element leaching concentration is lower than the regulatory limits

*UDL = under the detection limit

Fig. 8. Evaluation of SCM potential for wind turbine blade waste from different sources.

Table 11
Basic characteristics of different WTBW sources: A perspective on applications.

Material group	Physical characteristics	Chemical characteristics	Mineral characteristics	Morphological characteristics	Properties summary and their potential advantages	Potential applications	Standards/Compliance note
WTBW1	Particles with a similar size and low specific gravity	Silicates and alumina silicates. Medium resin content	Relatively medium amorphous minerals	Fiber shape	Relatively large particles reduce the water requirement and improve the workability of concrete [49,50]. Silicates and alumina silicates result in higher pozzolanic activity [51–53].	1. As workability-modifying admixtures. 2. As pozzolans.	EN 450–1 [59]: chemistry acceptable (high SAF); LOO high → pretreat or low dosage. EN 196–1 [60]: verify SAI if used as SCM. EN 12457–2 [25]: leaching pass (Cr, Cu, Pb, Mo, V).
WTBW2	Fine particles	Silicates and alumina silicates. Low resin content	Relatively high amorphous minerals	Irregular shape	Fine particles have better dissolution and nucleation, which improves the hydration of cement [54–56]. High amorphous minerals are also beneficial to cement hydration. Silicates and alumina silicates result in higher pozzolanic activity [51–53].	1. As strength-modifying admixtures. 2. As pozzolans.	EN 450–1 [59]: chemistry favorable; LOO still above typical limits → consider mild thermal cleaning or tighter dosage. EN 196–1 [60]: confirm SAI. EN 12457–2 [25]: leaching pass.
WTBW3	Fine particles	Silicates and alumina silicates. High resin content	Relatively low amorphous minerals	Irregular shape	Although fine particles have better dissolution and nucleation, high resin content leads to low amorphous minerals, hindering the cement hydration process [57, 58]. Silicates and alumina silicates result in more pozzolanic activity [51–53].	1. As retarders. 2. As pozzolans.	EN 450–1 [59]: LOO well above limits → not compliant without pretreatment; chemistry acceptable. EN 196–1: test SAI after pretreatment. EN 12457–2: leaching pass.

- WTBW1 is dominated by quartz from glass fibers. While WTBW2 exhibits rutile without notable calcite, and WTBW3 shows dominant calcite and a distinct s-triazine signal. All three WTBW display a broad hump ($\approx 15\text{--}30^\circ 2\theta$) indicating amorphous silica from the glass phase. These differences and similarities explain source-dependent reactivity pathways in alkaline pore solution.
- The textures of WTBW affect dispersion and nucleation potential in the cementitious matrix. WTBW1 presents clearer fiber-resin interfaces; WTBW2 shows roughened fibers with fragmented resin and better glass exposure; WTBW3 is resin-rich with fine glass fragments embedded, limiting surface availability.
- WTBW loses mass mainly between 200 and 400 °C (resin decomposition) and 400–600 °C (residual carbonates/calcite). DSC reveals T_g values $\sim 52.7^\circ\text{C}$ (WTBW1), 63.3°C (WTBW2), 58.6°C (WTBW3), and exothermic events at $\sim 134.6^\circ\text{C}$ (WTBW1), 165.8°C (WTBW2), 197.8°C (WTBW3), reflecting different resin formulations and curing degrees. Particularly, WTBW3 shows the largest total mass loss, consistent with higher organics.
- R^3 reactivity (20°C) shows the promising pozzolanic reactivity (around one third to half of the heat release of the reference calcined clay) in terms of the different sources of WTBW. Specifically, WTBW1 exhibits the fastest initial heat evolution and approaches $\sim 100\text{ J/g}$ by $\sim 168\text{ h}$; WTBW2 starts slowly but climbs late to a similar final heat; WTBW3 plateaus earlier near $\sim 80\text{ J/g}$. At 160 h, the relative heats confirm $\text{WTBW1} \approx \text{WTBW2} > \text{WTBW3}$.
- The different sources of WTBW indicate low leaching risk under the test protocol. For the elements measured (e.g., Cr, Cu, Pb), concentrations are generally below EU limits at $L/S = 10$, and only Pb was highest in WTBW2 but remained far below the regulatory limit.

WTBW contains a usable amorphous silicate phase and, with management of resin-rich fractions, can serve as an SCM. WTBW1 and WTBW2 show more favorable microstructure–reactivity combinations, while WTBW3 would benefit from pretreatment (e.g., additional grinding and/or thermal cleaning) to expose glass and reduce organics before use at higher replacement levels.

While the characterization suggests high SCM potential, it is acknowledged that formal validation through the Strength Activity Index (SAI) according to standards such as EN 196–1 [60] or ASTM C311 [61] is a necessary next step to quantify the chemical contribution to strength development. Although this study focuses on the physico-chemical characterization of WTBW, the practical feasibility of these materials as cement substitutes has been validated in our parallel research. As shown in the reference [9], replacements ranging from

2.5% to 15% demonstrated no significant loss in workability or consolidation issues at a standard water-to-binder ratio (w/b) of 0.4–0.5. This is attributed to the hydrophobic nature of the resin content, which prevents the internal absorption of mixing water that often complicates the rheology of porous or hydrophilic fillers.

Finally, as our previous research [27,62,63] indicate that shredded WTBW can function effectively as fiber reinforcement, future exploration should focus on the synergistic “dual-application” of this waste. Specifically, investigating the optimum ratio of powdered WTBW for cement replacement and fiber-like WTBW for reinforcement could maximize the material value in a single cementitious system, further supporting a circular economy in the wind energy sector.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ana Teresa Lima: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Liyun Yu:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ashal Tyurkay:** Writing – review & editing. **Javier Romero Gil:** Methodology, Investigation. **Charilaos Paraskevoulakos:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Tao Liu:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Normalized score for the evaluation of SCM potential.

	WTBW1	WTBW2	WTBW3
Normalized CPI	0.835	1	0.805
Normalized RBI	0.615	1	0
Normalized RRI	1	0.958	0.779
Normalized SPI	0.5	1	0
Normalized LCS	1	1	1

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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